

The European Chips Act, The *ISOLDE* Project, and Open-Source Hardware

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Abstract—This paper summarizes the latest advancements in the European Chips Act and gives an outlook of some of the planned contributions of Silicon Austria Labs (SAL) in the research project *ISOLDE*. Starting from the inception of the Chips Joint Undertaking (ChipsJU), the paper will then point out recent funding activities on RISC-V for High Performance Computing (HPC) and safety critical domains in Europe, before looking more closely to the research done by Silicon Austria Labs. We will describe our current work on implementing a Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) co-processor, incorporating the RISC-V Instruction Set Architecture (ISA) via OpenHW group’s CVA6. This co-processor and SAL’s Machine Learning (ML) co-processor, would eventually be incorporated into a System-on-Chip (SoC) implementing acceleration of distributed-learning tasks via Quantum-Safe Cryptography (QSC).

Index Terms—RISC-V, RISC-V Accelerator, ChipsJU, *ISOLDE*, PQC

I. INTRODUCTION

When NVIDIA announced plans to take-over the European CPU designer ARM in 2020, concerns on the competitiveness of Europe in the semiconductor area arose - especially in light of the fact that Europe was, at the time, experiencing the effects of the global chip shortage in addition to the ongoing challenges posed by COVID. The combination of these events awoke the European Commission (EC) to just how dependent Europe had become on non-EU countries such as the US, China, Taiwan, etc. in the semiconductor area.

These developments, and the ultimate realisation by the EU, led to the announcement of the European Chips Act[1] in the 2021 state of the union speech from Commission President Ursula von der Leyen [2]. Although the final definition and ratification of the European Chips Act would take some years, it finally came into effect in September 2023 with a financial commitment of more than EUR 43 billion by 2030. This is expected to be complemented by an equivalent amount of private funding [1]. Similar initiatives have been started on international level, e.g. the US Chips Act allows the allocation of USD 52 billion to manufacturing and R&D until 2026, China will invest USD 150 billion by 2025, Japan USD 21 billion, and South Korea plans to invest (together with companies) USD 450 billion in R&D and manufacturing until 2023 [3]. This sets the stage for a renewed race for the leadership in the semiconductor area.

In the remainder of this paper, we give a short overview of the key instruments defined by the European Chips Act and discuss the role of RISC-V and open hardware (HW). This is followed by a detailed look at some of SAL’s ongoing work on a RISC-V-based PQC co-processor design. In concluding the paper, we present our vision of a co-processor accelerated, distributed learning design with Quantum-Safe Cryptography to be provided in a System-on-Chip solution.

II. RISC-V: A EUROPEAN, AND EU, PERSPECTIVE

Notable European investment in RISC-V can be traced back to at least the European Processor Initiative¹ (EPI) that started around 2017 and aims at producing a low-power high-performance processor. Together with other partners of the project, the company SiPearl developed a CPU comprising ARM as well as RISC-V cores [4]. From these beginnings, a supporting foundation for RISC-V was grown through the European Commission’s other funding devices, prior to the context or execution of the European Chips Act.

A. European Chips Act and Technology Sovereignty

The European Chips Act has five objectives[1]:

- 1) Strengthening research and technological leadership
- 2) Improving capacity to design, manufacture, and package advanced chips
- 3) Creating a framework to increase production by 2030
- 4) Addressing the skills shortage and attracting new talent
- 5) Developing an in-depth understanding of global semiconductor supply chains

To achieve these objectives, three “action pillars” have been defined: (1) the *Chips for Europe Initiative*, (2) a framework ensuring the security of supply, and (3) a mechanism for monitoring semiconductor value chains.

Most interesting for researchers and engineers is the first pillar, which initiates Pilot Lines, Competence Centers, and a common design platform for IC manufacturing. Figure 1 shows the intended interplay between these elements; pilot lines help closing the gap between research and the deployment in production, competence centers shall address skill gaps, and the design platform shall make Electronic Design Automation (EDA) tools and Intellectual Property (IP)

¹<https://www.european-processor-initiative.eu/>

Figure 1. Overview of Pilot Lines, Competence Centers, and the Design Platform. Source: Chips for Europe Initiative [5]

easily accessible, especially for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and start-ups.

The Chips Joint Undertaking (ChipsJU²) has become responsible for setting up the various funding calls. This is an organization comprising members of the European Commission, Participating Member States, and private members. In a first call, about EUR 1.7 billion EU funding will be made available for pilot lines [6]; calling for proposals on *Fully Depleted Silicon on Insulator, Nodes below 2 nm, Heterogeneous Integration*, and *Wide Bandgap Semiconductors*. In parallel, calls for setting up competence centers and the design platform are being prepared; according to the Commission the design platform... [7]

... is a cloud-based virtual environment to be made available across the Union, integrating a wide range of design facilities, from IP libraries to Electronic Design Automation (EDA) tools, as well as support services. The platform will be accessible in an open, non-discriminatory and transparent way, stimulating wide cooperation between users and key actors of the ecosystem whilst reinforcing Europe’s chip design capacity.

The ChipsJU plays a pivotal role in initiating calls for research projects and has launched three dedicated calls on RISC-V since 2022. While the most recent call on “*High Performance RISC-V Automotive Processors supporting the vehicle of the future*” is still open at the time of writing, the previous calls led to projects such as *TRISTAN (Together for RISC-v Technology and Applications)*³ focusing on expanding the European RISC-V ecosystem and *ISOLDE (high performance, Safe, secure, Open-source Leveraged risc-v Domain-specific Ecosystem)*⁴ concentrating on high-performance RISC-V processing. The naming of these projects reflects their collaborative nature, complementing each other’s technical innovations.

Aside from the ChipsJU, the European Commission also followed up on the EPI-line of initiatives and published a call on a partnership for “*developing a large-scale European initiative for High Performance Computing (HPC) ecosystem based on RISC-V*” in late 2022 [8]. The idea is to develop prototypes and demonstrators of RISC-V-based HPC systems within a time-span of 6 years with an estimated funding of EUR 270 million - half provided by the Commission, the other half by the member states.

This movement towards RISC-V and open HW in general was also recommended by the *working group on open source HW and software* [9] in September 2022. In their report, the authors argue that “*the use of open source drastically lowers the barrier to design innovative SoCs which is an area that Europe excels in and strongly depends on in key application sectors*”. In addition, a special RISC-V automotive road-map is nearing completion (at the time of writing) and shall be published soon.

B. European RISC-V Ecosystem

Similar to the support available through the European Commission, the commercial ecosystem around RISC-V has been growing in Europe. A recent addition is the corporation *Quintauris*⁵, jointly founded by Bosch, Infineon, Nordic Semiconductor, NXP, and Qualcomm. According to information on their website, they “*aim to accelerate the commercialization of future products based on the open-source RISC-V architecture*”. Other well known companies include *SiPearl*⁶, *Codasip*⁷, *Gaisler*⁸, with companies such as *Axelera*⁹ working on accelerator designs for RISC-V.

As an example of the size that the RISC-V-based development community is growing to in Europe, we look at the example of the *TRISTAN* project which comprises 46 partner organisations across Europe, including NXP, Bosch, ST,

²<https://www.chips-ju.europa.eu/>

³<https://www.tristan-project.eu/>

⁴<https://www.isolde-project.eu/>

⁵<https://www.quintauris.eu/>

⁶<https://sipearl.com>

⁷<https://codasip.com/>

⁸<https://www.gaisler.com/>

⁹<https://www.axelera.ai/>

GreenWaves, Infineon, Siemens, Leonardo, Thales, Semify, Codasip.

As a result of Europe’s renewed focus on semiconductors, TSMC announced a joint venture with Infineon, Bosch, and NXP called *European Semiconductor Manufacturing Company* (ESMC). After a planned investment of EUR 10 billion, the new chip plant located in Germany, Dresden, will produce 22 nm and 16 nm chips [10]. Other relevant investments include Intel’s decision to break ground on a chip plant in Magdeburg, Germany with plans to manufacture in 1.5 nm technology [11]. Even though these developments are not directly related to the RISC-V development community, they will strengthen the European semiconductor domain.

C. Challenges for Open Hardware

While the momentum behind RISC-V and open HW is encouraging, especially for academics and researchers, one of the main challenges is navigating the *export control* regulations of the European Union [12]. Annex I of the regulation defines a catalog of dual-use items that need an export license to legally be exported. While export control usually is not relevant for basic research as well as open source software, open HW designs could potentially be subject to these regulations [12].

As a specific example from the regulation, Section 3A001.a.9 categorizes *neural network integrated circuits* as dual-use/export controlled items. Similarly, Section 5A002.a explicitly mentions a number of post-quantum cryptosystems. Apart from defining the export controlled items, the regulation also lists general export authorisations in Annex II. For instance, the general export authorisation EU001 permits export to countries like Switzerland, USA, Japan, Canada, among others, under certain conditions [12].

While research projects may be eligible for certain exceptions, developers engaged in open HW development need to keep the export control regulations in mind. Depending on the nature of their work, they might need to apply for an export license to ensure compliance with the regulations.

III. THE ISOLDE PROJECT

A. Project Objectives

The *ISOLDE* project received initial approval for funding via the Key Digital Technologies Joint Undertaking (KDT-JU) initiative in 2022¹⁰, specifically from *Innovation Action 1, Focus Topic 3: "Design of Customizable and Domain Specific Open-Source RISC-V Processors"*. *ISOLDE* is comprised of a consortium of 38 partner universities, Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs), and corporations across Europe. The development focus of each partner is spread across a number of topic-focused work packages including:

- 1) Further developing and verifying existing RISC-V open HW processor designs (CVA6, NOEL-V), including various peripherals for such designs.

- 2) Design and verification of a number of RISC-V integrate-able accelerator designs; General focus of this work include safety & security, processor monitoring, AI & SIMD/vector, cryptography, neuromorphic computing, and signal processing.
- 3) Compiler, HW emulation/validation, and other software infrastructure for RISC-V generally and accelerators; Includes work on drivers, libraries, and design/test automation software.
- 4) Multiple use case demonstrators to display the usefulness/possibilities for exploitation of the project’s output.
- 5) Dissemination and publication of learning materials and documentation specifically related to RISC-V and *ISOLDE* project outputs.

B. SAL’s Focus: Post-Quantum Cryptography & Accelerators

While SAL’s activities on Neural-Network (NN) accelerators are described in a separate paper [13], we focus on our PQC related activities in this article. Quantum computing has the ability to speed up complex and difficult mathematical calculations, for e.g., the discrete-logarithm or prime factorisation problems using Shor’s algorithm [14] and the unstructured search problems using Grover’s algorithm [15]. Currently, the most commonly employed types of Digital Signature Algorithm (DSA) and Public Key Encryption (PKE) techniques involve the solutions to problems involving prime integer factorization (for Rivest–Shamir–Adleman algorithm [16]), discrete logarithms (for DSA/ElGamal encryption), and the Elliptic-curve Diffie–Hellman protocol [17]. PQC is an emerging field that involves the study and definition of security algorithms and cryptosystems that are secure against attacks that exploit advantages inherently provided to processing performed by quantum computers [18].

Currently, the developed algorithms which are considered quantum safe mainly fall into two categories or coding types:

- 1) Lattice-based ciphers; which rely upon the Learning With Errors (LWE) problem.
- 2) Code-based ciphers; which rely on syndrome decoding problems.

Implementing quantum-safe cryptographic algorithms on HW is a major task in *ISOLDE* as secure communication, including forward security and future security, is a key requirement of any modern embedded system. Some of the partners working on the PQC task in *ISOLDE* are focusing on implementing algorithm-complete accelerators for PQCs such as *HQC* [19], *BiKE* [20], *CRYSTALS-KYBER* [21], and *Classic McEliece* [22]. An alternative approach is to accelerate the PQC *primitives*; this may include algorithms for memory-management of large keys, Number Theoretic Transforms (NTT [23]) for polynomial multiplications or other polynomial multiplication algorithms.

C. NTT Acceleration

The NTT has been the subject of much research related to PQC algorithms and Homomorphic Encryption (HE) in

¹⁰KDT-JU has since been consolidated into ChipsJU

Figure 2. SAL's PQC Co-Processor Architecture. Turquoise/dark parts to be developed by SAL.

recent years. Via the use of convolution theorem, it provides a method to facilitate the processing of an otherwise expensive operation, both analytically and computationally [24]. It allows to perform the multiplication of two discrete polynomials, which is a linear convolution in the finite field as a much simpler, point-wise, multiplication operation. With NTT, frequently-used, complex computational operations in PQC can be made quasi-linear, or “linearithmic” with time complexity of $O(n \log n)$ compared to polynomial with a time complexity of $O(n^2)$ [25]. As NTT is a specialised case of the fast Fourier Transform (FFT) applied to finite fields, we are also exploring HW implementations which can be used flexibly for both FFTs and NTTs in space-constrained settings.

The NTT has been the topic of much research in the area of HW acceleration in the last decade [25], with particular attention paid to its use for the acceleration of lattice-based PQC [26], [27], [28] and HE schemes [29], [30] in recent years. Recent years have also seen code-based algorithms such as Classic McEliece being explored for NTT-based HW acceleration [31], [32].

1) *Our Ongoing Implementation:* The architecture of our full implementation in *ISOLDE*, shown in Figure 2, involves multiple open-HW modules along with the modules developed at SAL. It is a standard-cell based Application Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) incorporating a CVA6, AXI-4 Bus, SRAM blocks, and various peripheral/interface-bridge IPs and our own co-processor that focuses on processing PQC primitives. Open-source projects such as Litex¹¹ and the PULP

platform¹² offer a robust suite of peripherals and interface bridges designed to facilitate the development of complex digital systems, simplifying our design and verification process for the work.

Our core RISC-V processor is the Open-HW Group’s CVA6. It has seen widespread adoption for RISC-based PQC designs in recent years with its ability to extend the RISC-V instruction set for PQC operations via the Core-V eXtension interface (CV-X-IF [33], [32]). This allows the implementation of a PQC Instruction Set Extension (ISE) on-top of the RISC-V standard Instruction Set Architecture (ISA), capable of speeding up the computations compared to any memory-mapped solution [34]. The current risk with this implementation scheme is that the CV-X-IF is still in “beta” version (number 0.2.0 at the time of writing). However, it has been adopted for two core designs and with two co-processors currently - PULP’s *Ara* [35] for the CVA6 and a Floating Point Unit (FPU) for the *CV32E40P* [33]. We hope to have a partial implementation of RISC-V’s ongoing PQC ISE¹³.

For our co-processor, we draw inspiration from a number of papers [32] that proposed a method of PQC acceleration and existing non-PQC-based co-processors, particularly PULP’s vector co-processor, *Ara* [35], [36]. The PQC co-processor will contain NTT & Inverse NTT (INTT) accelerators, targeted specifically for the large key sizes involved in code-based PQC schemes. In addition, an accelerator for non-NTT based polynomial multiplications may be designed and included

¹¹<https://github.com/enjoy-digital/litex>

¹²<https://github.com/pulp-platform/axi>

¹³<https://github.com/riscv/riscv-crypto>

Figure 3. Overview of SAL’s planned quantum-safe edge-ML SoC Architecture. Turquoise/dark parts developed by SAL.

to provide better performance for the symmetric-key portion of lattice-based communications. One final module we may decide to include is a memory management unit for the larger-keys to boost efficiency and security in key storage and retrieval, with the additional functionality of improving security against Side Channel Attacks and error-detection/correction.

Figure 2 also shows *Decode* blocks that are responsible for receiving commands from the CV-X-IF interface (also checking their validity) and decide how/where to execute or offload the instruction. Similarly, the *Result Processing* blocks send commands back to the processor or co-processor instruction buffer, write processed instruction results to memory, or flag any issues.

IV. TOWARDS AN INTEGRATED SOLUTION

SAL’s vision is to combine the PQC accelerator with an ML domain co-processor in one integrated SoC for HW accelerated, quantum-safe, distributed learning. Figure 3 gives a basic description of the intended final architecture.

While SAL’s NN-accelerator design is more advanced and mature [13], it is geared towards supporting inference operations on already defined networks. In order to have efficient, distributed Edge-AI, we will need to add HW acceleration for in-service learning and on-the-fly model exchange through PQC-secured communication.

Software design for architectures such as ours, and more generally in the context of RISC-V’s current heterogeneous HW landscape, is another focus of our research. From the software developer’s perspective, it would be advantageous to handle these architectures agnostically and without significant loss of performance due to accelerator availability. As such, our goal is to develop a modular compiler that not only optimizes software to specific architectures but also ensures compatibility across heterogeneous HW, enabling the compilation of code

on various HW platforms without the necessity to dedicate a lot of work to accommodate a particular device.

To this end, we seek to exploit the Multi-Level Intermediate Representation (MLIR [37]) framework. It provides a more flexible approach to compilation with a gradual lowering of code abstraction to object code, while enabling optimization at each stage. The framework seems particularly well-suited for the heterogeneous landscape of RISC-V HW, as depending on the availability of an accelerator or co-processor, optimization layers can be skipped and the relevant instructions for the accelerator inserted. In cases where no accelerator is present, Base-ISA object code is produced, ensuring adaptability and optimization in any HW configurations. This is not to mention MLIR’s native ability for better optimization through the use of higher-level, abstract optimization stages not present in classic compilers[38], among others.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The EU Chips Act and the consortia formed for projects such as *ISOLDE* and *TRISTAN* present a strategic opportunity to establish a novel open HW platform. SAL aims to leverage these efforts towards implementing HW accelerators, particularly targeted towards PQC and NN algorithms. Within the *ISOLDE* project, we explore diverse demonstrator cases for our accelerators for automotive and space applications. The platform architecture consists a CVA6 RISC-V processor which interfaces with a dedicated accelerator co-processor. We are currently running simulations on the processor design, working in collaboration with the other partners in the consortium to ensure uniformity of processor parameters. Upon finalizing the HW design, the next milestone involves a tape-out of an SoC with the accelerator which can then be used for the test demonstrators.

To support the open HW initiative, we aim at releasing some of our PQC designs as open HW; Keeping in mind Europe’s export control regulations, which might impose some limitations on what we can release openly. However, one might argue that as our designs are done on a prototype research level they may not meet all requirements regarding cybersecurity that one expects from a fully industrial implementation.

Finally, we will conduct research on necessary changes to compilers and libraries, so that SW developers and engineers might use new HW features without having to resort to massive code changes of existing code bases or dealing with code in very low-levels of abstraction. This will build the foundation of our HW accelerated, quantum-safe cryptography based distributed learning platform.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research received funding from the Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG) and the Austrian ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology (BMK) under project no. FO999899263 and funding from the Chips Joint Undertaking under project no. 101112274 (*ISOLDE*) and its members Austria, Czechia, France, Germany, Italy, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland.

The opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and should not be considered as representative of the European Commission's official position.

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